

BACTERIOLOGICAL PROFILE AND ANTIMICROBIAL SUSCEPTIBILITY PATTERN OF OPEN FRACTURE WOUND ISOLATES IN UPPER AND LOWER LIMB: A STUDY FROM TERTIARY CARE CENTER OF THE SUB-HIMALAYAN REGION OF INDIA

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ABSTRACT

Background: Open fractures are high-risk injuries prone to infection due to direct communication with the external environment. These injuries are often associated with high-energy trauma and require prompt surgical intervention and targeted antimicrobial therapy. Understanding the demographic distribution, mechanisms of injury, and microbiological spectrum is essential for effective management.

Material and Method: This study is a retrospective analysis of the bacteriological profile and antimicrobial susceptibility pattern of open fracture wound isolates in upper and lower limb organisms over a period of 1 year, i.e., from April 2023 to March 2024. All samples were processed as per standard Microbiological guidelines. Antimicrobial susceptibility was done by the Kirby-Bauer disk diffusion method as per CLSI guidelines.

Results: Open fractures were more common in males (87%), with the 31–50 age group most affected.

Road accidents were the leading cause (61%), mostly involving the lower limb (71%). Culture positivity was higher in lower limb fractures (28.2%) than in upper limbs (24.1%). *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus* were the predominant pathogens. Colistin and Vancomycin showed the highest sensitivity among Gram-negative and Gram-positive isolates, respectively.

Discussion and conclusion: Lower limb open fractures are more prone to infection, with a broader spectrum of pathogens. The predominance of *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*, along with varying antimicrobial resistance patterns, underscores the importance of regular microbiological surveillance and antibiotic stewardship in managing open fractures.

Keywords: Clinical Laboratory Standard Institute, MSSA-Methicillin-sensitive *Staphylococcus aureus*, MRSA-Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*.

INTRODUCTION

An open fracture is an injury where the skin and surrounding soft tissues are broken, exposing the fractured bone to the external environment. This exposure directly connects the bone or blood clot (hematoma) and the outside, often leading to bacterial contamination.¹

Open fractures are typically caused by traumatic incidents such as car crashes, falls from significant heights, blunt force injuries, or accidents involving farming equipment. These injuries often result in extensive damage to the skin, muscles, blood vessels, and nerves. Infection is a frequent complication in such cases.²

Open fractures are commonly classified using the Gustilo-Anderson system, which provides valuable insights for prognosis and treatment.³

When the blood supply to the injury site is compromised, the body's immune response weakens. During the initial two hours, the immune system attempts to lower the overall bacterial count. In the following four hours, a balance is established between bacterial growth and the body's defense mechanisms, leading to a relatively stable bacterial population.⁴

Beyond the first six hours, invading bacteria rapidly multiply in the presence of abundant necrotic tissue, leading to a clinical infection.⁵

Patients with open fractures often present with typical clinical signs of infection, such as redness, warmth, pain, swelling, and impaired function. These infections can lead to sepsis and potentially fatal outcomes.⁶

Open fractures are highly susceptible to bacterial contamination, leading to serious infections that can delay healing, increase morbidity, and prolong hospital stays. Understanding the bacteriological profile and antimicrobial susceptibility pattern of these wound isolates is crucial for effective management and infection control. Given the rising threat of antimicrobial resistance, identifying susceptibility patterns is essential for optimizing treatment strategies, reducing complications, and improving patient outcomes.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

This present study was conducted in the Department of Microbiology of Dr Rajendra Prasad Medical College and Hospital, Kangra at Tanda, Himachal Pradesh over a period of one year from April 2023 to March 2024 in collaboration with the Department of Orthopedics. A total of 100 patients were included in the studies who were admitted after surgeries for open fractures in the ward of the Department of Orthopedics.

Aseptically collected wound swabs from each patient on the 5th or 6th day of postoperative day. and inoculated on 5% Blood agar plates and MacConkey agar plates and incubated aerobically at 37°C for 24 hours. Culture plates with bacterial growth were considered for Gram staining, and biochemical reactions were carried out for identification.⁷

Antimicrobial susceptibility testing was done according to the standard operational procedures. In vitro antimicrobial susceptibility testing was done on Mueller-Hinton agar (Hi-Media Lab Ltd, India) using the Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion method. The test organisms were suspended in sterile normal saline, and turbidity was adjusted to 0.5 McFarland standards. The test organism was uniformly seeded over the surface of Mueller-Hinton agar plates. The plates were allowed to dry for 15 minutes before the application of antibiotic discs. The plates

were incubated at 37°C for 16-18 hours. After incubation, clear zones around the antibiotic discs were measured with a ruler and recorded in millimeters. Susceptibility and resistance data were interpreted according to Clinical Laboratory Standards Institute guidelines, and antimicrobial susceptibility was performed according to CLSI guidelines⁸

RESULT

A total of 100 patients with open fractures were included in this study, conducted in the Department of Microbiology at Dr.RPGMC Kangra at Tanda over one year, from April 2023 to March 2024.

The study population had a male-to-female ratio of 6.69:1, with males comprising 87% of the cases and females accounting for the remaining 13%.

SEX WISE DISTRIBUTION

Figure 1: Distribution of subjects on the basis of sex

Age-wise distribution of patients in this study, the mean age of the study participants was 42.23 years with a range from 18 years to 83 years. The majority (48%) of the subjects were between 31 and 50 years of age followed by 28% at 18 to 30 years, 17% between 51 and 70 years, and the remaining 7% above 70 years.

Figure 2: Distribution of subjects on the basis of age.

This study included a total of 100 patients with open fractures. Roadside accidents were the leading cause, accounting for 61% of cases, followed by falls from heights, which contributed to 29%. Trauma caused by stones or weapons constituted a smaller but significant proportion, representing 10% of cases.

Figure 3: Cause of open fractures-based distribution of study participants.

In this study, all patients sustained injuries to the appendicular skeleton, with the lower limb being affected in 71% of cases and the upper limb in 29%. Notably, no injuries to the axial skeleton were reported.

Figure 4: Distribution of open fractures in the study population

The most frequent site of fracture was the lower limb, with the highest incidence seen in both bones of leg 31(31 %), followed by fractures of the tibia 19 (19 %) and femur 15 (15 %). Fractures of the upper limb are also notable, with the humerus and radius each accounting for 7 % of cases, while the ulna and both bones forearm have 4 and 6 cases, respectively. Fractures of the Patella, Fibula, and Hand are less common, with 3 cases each, and the least frequent sites include the foot and axial Skeleton, with 2 and 0 cases, respectively.

Figure 5: Site of fractures

Organisms isolated in the upper limb open fracture

Out of 29 cases of open upper limb fractures, 21 cases (72.4%) showed no microbial growth, while 7 cases (24.1%) were culture-positive for infection. Both Gram-positive and Gram-

negative bacteria were isolated from the infected wounds. Among the Gram-negative isolates, the most frequently identified organism was *Escherichia coli*, 4 isolates (50%), followed by *Enterobacter aerogenes* in 2 isolates (25%). *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Citrobacter freundii* were less commonly isolated. Among the Gram-positive isolates, *Staphylococcus aureus* was the predominant organism, identified in 2 isolates (28.5%).

Figure 6: Isolated organism in upper limb open fracture

Antimicrobial susceptibility pattern among Gram-negative bacteria in the Upper limb open fracture.

Among gram-negative bacteria, maximum susceptibility was seen to Colistin (100%), followed by Meropenem (85%), and the least susceptibility was seen for Ceftazidime (55%).

Figure 7: Antimicrobial susceptibility pattern among Gram-negative bacteria in the Upper limb open fracture.

Antimicrobial susceptibility pattern among Gram-positive bacteria in the Upper limb

A total of two MRSA isolates were recovered from an upper limb open fracture. Both isolates exhibited an identical susceptibility pattern. They are: Sensitive to: Vancomycin, clindamycin, and resistant to cefoxitin, penicillin, and Azithromycin.

Organisms isolated in the Lower limb open fracture

Out of a total of 71 open lower limb fracture cases, 51 (71.8%) yielded sterile cultures, while 20 (28.2%) were culture-positive, indicating infection. The positive cultures revealed both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacterial isolates. Among the Gram-negative isolates, *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* were the most common, each accounting for 20% of the isolates. *Acinetobacter baumannii* constituted 10%, while *Enterobacter aerogenes* and *Serratia marcescens* were the least frequent, with one isolate each (5%). Among the Gram-positive isolates, *Staphylococcus aureus* was the predominant organism (45%), followed by *Enterococcus faecalis* (10%).

Figure 8: Organisms isolated in the Lower limb open fracture.

Antimicrobial susceptibility pattern among Gram-negative bacteria in the lower limb

Among gram-negative bacteria, maximum susceptibility was seen to Colistin (100%), followed by Meropenem (75%), and the least susceptibility was seen for Ceftazidime (40%).

Figure 9: Antimicrobial susceptibility pattern among Gram-negative bacteria in the lower limb

Antimicrobial susceptibility pattern among Gram-positive bacteria in the lower limb

Among gram-positive isolates, maximum susceptibility was seen to Vancomycin (100%) followed by Clindamycin (60%), and the least susceptibility was seen for Penicillin (10%).

Figure 10: Antimicrobial susceptibility pattern among Gram-positive bacteria in the lower limb

DISCUSSION

In our study, open fractures were more common in males (87%) than females (13%), with a male-to-female ratio of 6.7:1, consistent with findings by Gupta et al. and Agarwal et al.^{9,10} This disparity may be due to males engaging in riskier activities like high-speed driving and extreme sports. The mean age of patients was 42.23 years, with the 31–50 age group being the most affected (48%), similar to Villa PEA et al.'s study.¹¹ This age group is more involved in outdoor and physically demanding occupations, increasing their risk of injury.

Roadside accidents were the leading cause of open fractures (61%), aligning with studies by Islam S et al.¹² and other African studies. Factors such as poorly maintained roads, challenging mountainous terrain, adverse weather, and increased tourist traffic in Himachal Pradesh contribute to this high incidence. The lower limb was most frequently affected (71%), likely due to its direct exposure in accidents, which matches findings by Hasan Obada et al.¹ Fractures involving both bones of the leg were most common (31%), followed by tibia (19%) and femur fractures (15%), consistent with Shah I et al.¹³ Open tibial fractures pose a high risk of complications due to their anatomical vulnerability. In our study, we observed an infection rate of 28.2% in open fractures of the lower limb and 24.1% in open fractures of the upper limb. In support of our findings study conducted by Maheshwari *et al* rate of infection was found to be higher in lower limb fractures as 25% of cultures were positive in lower limb fractures as compared to 16.7% in upper limb fractures.¹⁴ upper limb fractures, 24.1% showed microbial growth, with both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria isolated. *Escherichia coli* was the most common Gram-negative organism (50%), followed by *Enterobacter aerogenes*. Among Gram-positive isolates, *Staphylococcus aureus* was predominant (28.5%). The predominance of *E. coli* in upper limb fracture infections is notable and may be associated with contamination from environmental or nosocomial sources, Gram-negative isolates showed the highest susceptibility to Colistin (100%) and Meropenem (85%), with the

lowest to Ceftazidime (55%). Two MRSA isolates were sensitive to Vancomycin and Clindamycin, but resistant to Cefoxitin, Penicillin, and Azithromycin. These findings highlight the need for regular monitoring and antibiotic stewardship. In lower limb open fractures, 28.2% of cases showed positive cultures, with both Gram-negative and Gram-positive organisms isolated. *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa* were the most common Gram-negative pathogens (20% each), while *A. Baumannii* and others were less frequent. Among Gram-positive isolates, *S. aureus* (45%) was predominant, followed by *E. faecalis*. The higher culture positivity and diverse microbial profile in lower limb open fractures may be due to greater tissue damage, increased contamination risk from road traffic accidents, and delayed wound coverage compared to upper limb injuries. Gram-positive bacteria from lower limb isolates showed the highest susceptibility to Vancomycin (100%) and the least to Penicillin (10%). A similar pattern was observed compared to upper limb isolates, though Clindamycin sensitivity was slightly higher in upper limbs. Gram-negative isolates from the lower limb were most sensitive to Colistin (100%) and least to Ceftazidime (40%). Upper limb isolates showed slightly better Meropenem sensitivity. The differences in susceptibility between upper and lower limb isolates may be attributed to variation in wound contamination, vascular supply, or frequency of healthcare-associated exposures.

CONCLUSION

Open fractures were significantly more common in males, with the lower limb being the most frequently affected, primarily due to road traffic accidents. The 31–50 age group was most vulnerable, likely due to occupational exposure and high physical activity. Culture positivity was slightly higher in lower limb fractures, with *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus* being the predominant pathogens. Vancomycin and Colistin remained the most effective antibiotics against Gram-positive and Gram-negative isolates, respectively. These findings emphasize the importance of regional antibiograms and tailored antibiotic stewardship to manage open fracture infections effectively.

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